

Abstract

The Effects of *Qigong* on Menopausal Symptoms and Quality of Life: A Preliminary Integrative Study.

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Abstract

Objective: This study aimed to evaluate whether *Qigong* can improve vegetative functions, symptom perception, emotional stability, and quality of life in postmenopausal women for whom Hormone Replacement Therapy (HRT) is contraindicated.

Materials and Methods: From an initial pool of 68 clinical appointments at a menopause department, eleven postmenopausal women (aged 36–59 years) were recruited. Inclusion criteria required a diagnosis of menopausal syndrome validated by an independent gynaecologist, a medical contraindication to HRT, and provided written informed consent. Participants underwent eight weeks of specific *Qigong* training. Clinical manifestations were assessed using the Kupperman Index, while emotional well-being was monitored via the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) and the World Health Organization Quality of Life (WHOQOL-BREF) scale. Additionally, salivary cortisol levels were measured as an objective physiological biomarker for stress.

Results: All clinical scores showed progressive improvement over the intervention period. Significant reductions ($p < 0.05$) were observed in the Kupperman Index (44%) and depression scores (14%), alongside a 10% improvement across all quality-of-life parameters. At the sub-scale level, significant positive regressions were recorded for vasomotor symptoms, paraesthesia, insomnia, fatigue, arthralgia, myalgia, headaches, palpitations, and vertigo; however, improvements in nervousness, melancholia, and anxiety did not reach statistical significance. Although salivary cortisol levels decreased by 40% over the eight weeks, these results were not statistically significant. No significant correlation was found between psychometric parameters and cortisol fluctuations.

Conclusions: *Qigong* significantly improved the perception of menopausal symptoms, reduced depressive symptoms, and enhanced the overall quality of life within this patient cohort. These findings suggest that *Qigong* is a viable therapeutic alternative for managing menopause when conventional hormonal treatments are unavailable. While these preliminary results are promising, further research with a larger sample size and a more robust methodology is recommended..

Keywords: Menopause; Vasomotor Symptoms; *Qigong*; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Biofeedback Therapy; Quality of Life.

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